

Pyrazoles from 3-formylchromone-ethyl vinyl ether adduct

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Reaction of (*E*)- β -(4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-yl)acrolein (**2**) with phenylhydrazine yields (*E*)- β -(4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-yl)acrolein phenylhydrazone (**4**) and [1-phenyl-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)pyrazol-4-yl]acrolein phenylhydrazone (**5**). 3-[(*E,E*)-5-Oxohexa-1,3-dien-1-yl]-1-benzopyran-4-one-5-phenylhydrazone (**6**) and phenylhydrazone (**7**) of 6-[5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl]hexa-3,4,5,6-dien-2-one have been synthesized by the reaction of 3-[(*E,E*)-5-oxohexa-1,3-dien-1-yl]-1-benzopyran-4-one (**3**) with phenylhydrazine. 4-[(*E*)-2-(3-Methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-yl)vinyl]-1-phenyl-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)pyrazole (**8**) is obtained from **7** by refluxing in nitrobenzene.

Pyrazoles exhibit various biological and pharmacological activities. In continuation of our work on 3-formylchromone-ethyl vinyl ether adduct **1**¹, we now report the synthesis of pyrazoles from the aldehyde **2**² and the ketone **3**¹ obtained by treatment of the adduct **1** with acetone in 50% H₂SO₄.

Chromone and its derivatives such as flavone and isoflavone offer two possible points of attack to nucleophiles such as amines and substituted amines^{3,4}. It appeared of interest, therefore, to study the reactions of **2** and **3** with phenylhydrazine. Compounds **2** and **3** gave with one

Scheme 1

equivalent of phenylhydrazine the corresponding phenylhydrazones **4** and **6** which cyclized in refluxing nitrobenzene to 1-phenyl-5-(4-oxo-1-benzopyran-3-yl)pyrazole⁵ and 3-[(*E*)-2-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5-yl)vinyl]-1-benzopyran-4-one¹ respectively. However, when an excess quantity of phenylhydrazine was used and the reaction mixture refluxed for several hours, chromone ring opened up to afford the pyrazoles **5** and **7**, the latter cyclizing to **8** in refluxing nitrobenzene (Scheme 1).

Experimental

M.ps. were taken on a Kofler block and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-3-100 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on Bruker 001 and VAT 100 instruments (300 and 90 MHz).

[1-Phenyl-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)pyrazol-4-yl]acrolein phenylhydrazone (5): A mixture of **2** (0.15 mmol) and phenylhydrazine (0.3 mmol) dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.1 ml) was refluxed on a boiling water-bath for 5 h and then allowed to stand at room temperature. On cooling, (*E*)-β-(4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-yl)acroleinphenylhydrazone (**4**) was obtained as yellow needles (12%). It was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated and left at room temperature when **5** crystallized out as yellow flakes (32%), m.p. 240°; ν_{\max} 3760 (OH), 3320 cm⁻¹ (NH), δ 6.26 (1H, d, H_a, *J* 16.8 Hz), 6.67–7.56 (16H, m, ArH + H_b + HC=N–N), 8.20 (1H, s, H_d), 9.69 (1H, br s, exchangeable NH), 10.01 (1H, br s, exchangeable OH); *m/z* 380 (M⁺, 100), 361 (5), 288 (13), 247 (26), 92 (25), 91 (25) and 77 (55).

Phenylhydrazone 7 of 6-[5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1-pyrazol-4-yl]hexa-3,4,5,6-dien-2-one: A mixture of **3** (2 mmol) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml), glacial acetic acid (0.05 ml) and phenylhydrazine (4 mmol) was refluxed on a boiling water-bath for 0.5 h and then allowed to stand at room temperature. On cooling, 3-[(*E,E*)-5-oxohexa-1,3-dien-1-yl]-

1-benzopyran-4-one-5-phenylhydrazone (**6**) crystallized out as shining yellow needles (30%). The mother liquor was then concentrated and kept at room temperature to give **7** as deep yellow granules. It was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated, extracted with ether and the ethereal extract chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh). Elution of the column with chloroform-petrol (b.p. 60–80°) (60 : 40, v/v) afforded more **7** (40%), m.p. 195–200°, ν_{\max} 3500 (OH), 3100 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.97 (3H, s, –N=C–CH₃), 6.13–7.36 (18H, m, ArH and olefinic H), 8.12 (1H, s, pyrazole H), 9.168 (1H, br s, NH), 9.66 (1H, br s, OH); *m/z* 420 (M⁺, 25), 419 (79), 328 (25), 327 (100), 245 (56), 170 (15), 91 (18) and 77 (38).

4-[(E)-2-(3-Methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-yl)vinyl]-1-phenyl-5-(2-hydroxyphenylpyrazole) (8): Compound **7** (0.2 g) taken in nitrobenzene (10 ml) was refluxed on an oil-bath for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was then adsorbed on a column of silica gel (60–120 mesh) and eluted with benzene-ethyl acetate (80 : 20, v/v). Appropriate fractions were combined, evaporated and crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether to afford **8** as colourless crystals (100 mg), m.p. 129–30°; δ 2.18 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.36 (1H, s, H_a), 6.56–7.44 (16H, m, ArH and –CH_b=CH_c–), 8.04 (1H, s, H_d), 9.72 (1H, s, exchangeable OH); *m/z* 418 (M⁺, 87), 417 (61), 401 (8), 323 (8), 92 (5), 90 (15), 84 (25), 82 (35) and 77 (100).

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